

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF USING TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH

Pulatova Zamira Abdullayevna
Teacher of Urgench State University
E-mail: pulatova77@bk.ru

Annotation. This article enlightens the role and importance of using technology in teaching English language.

Key words: technology, development, effective, internet, multimedia, process.

Аннотация: Эта статья просвещает роль и важность использования технологий в преподавании английского языка.

Ключевые слова: технология, развитие, эффективный, интернет, мультимедиа.

The new era assigns new challenges and duties on the modern teacher. The tradition of English teaching has been drastically changed with the remarkable entry of technology. Technology provides so many options as making teaching interesting and also making teaching more productive in terms of improvements. “Technology is one of the most significant drivers of both social and linguistic change. Technology lies at the heart of the globalization process affecting education work and culture. The use of English language has increased rapidly after 1960. At present the role and status of English is that it is the language of social context, political, sociocultural, business, education, industries, media, library, communication across borders, and key subject in curriculum and language of imparting education”.¹

It is also a crucial determinant for university entrance and processing well paid jobs in the commercial sector. Since there are more and more English learners in Uzbekistan, different teaching methods have been implemented to test the effectiveness of the teaching process. One method involves multimedia in ELT in order to create English contexts. This helps students to get involved and learn according to their interests. It has been tested effectively and is widely accepted for teaching English in modern world.

Technology is utilized for the uplifting of modern styles; it satisfies both visual and auditory senses of the students. With the spread and development

¹ Sharma R.K. Problems and Solutions of Teaching English. – New Delhi: JankiPrakashan, 1999. – p. 93.

of English around the world, English has been learned and used by more and more speakers. According to David Graddol “It is the language at the leading edge of scientific and technological development, new thinking in economics and management, new literatures and entertainment genre....”²

As the use of English has increased in popularity so has the need for qualified teachers to instruct students in the language. It is true that there are teachers who use cutting edge‘ technology, but the majority of teachers still teach in the traditional manner. None of these traditional manners are bad or damaging the students. In fact, till date they are proving to be useful also. However, there are many more opportunities for students to gain confidence practice and extend themselves, especially for ESL students who learn the language for more than just fun. For them to keep pace with ELT and gain more confidence they have to stride into the world of multimedia technology.

The 21 st century is the age of globalization and is important to grasp on various foreign languages and English language comes first. English Language Teaching has been with us for many years and its significance continues to grow, fuelled, partially by the Internet. Graddol’s study suggests that in the year 2000 there were about a billion English learners but a decade later the numbers doubled. The forecast points to a surge in English learning, which has peaked in 2010. The same study indicates that over 80% of information stored on the internet is in English. For the first time there are more Non-Native than Native users of the language and diversity of context in terms of learners, age, nationality, learning background etcetera has become a defining characteristic of ELT today.

With the rapid development of science and technology, the emerging and developing of multimedia technology and its application to teaching, featuring audio, visual, animation effects comes into full play in English class teaching and sets a favorable platform for reform and exploration on English teaching model in the new era. It’s proved that multimedia technology plays a positive role in promoting activities and initiatives of student and teaching effect in English class. Technological innovations have gone hand –in hand with the growth of English and are changing the way in which we communicate. It is fair to assert that the growth of the internet has facilitated the growth of the English language and that this has occurred at a time when computers are no longer the exclusive domains of the dedicated few, but rather available to many.

² David G.E. The future of English. –New Delhi: JankiPrakashan, 1999. – p. 2.

With this there has been a very significant proliferation of literature regarding the use of technology in teaching English language. Mostly these writings unequivocally accept technology as the most essential part in teaching. In a sense, a tendency to emphasize on inevitable role of technology in pedagogy to the extent of obliterating human part of teacher by technology part has been very dominant. And as a result if we neglect or ignore technological developments they will continue and perhaps we will never be able to catch up, irrespective of our discipline or branch. For this reason it is important for language teachers to be aware of the latest and best equipment and to have a full knowledge of what is available in any given situation. Teachers can use Multimedia Technology to give more colorful, stimulating lectures (new Horizons).

There are many techniques applicable in various degrees to language learning situation. Some are useful for testing and distance education, and some for teaching business English, spoken English, reading, listening or interpreting. The teaching principle should be to appreciate new technologies in the areas and functions where they provide something decisively new useful and never let machines take over the role of the teacher or limit functions where more traditional ways are superior. There are various reasons why all language learners and teachers must know how to make use of the new technology. Here we also need to emphasize that the new technologies develop and disseminate so quickly that we cannot avoid their attraction and influence in any form.

In the last few years the number of teachers using Computer -Assisted Language Learning (CALL) has increased markedly and numerous articles have been written about the role of technology in education in the 21st century. Although the potential of the Internet for educational use has not been fully explored yet and the average school still makes limited use of computers, it is obvious that we have entered a new information age in which the links between technology and TEFL have already been established. The development of the Internet brought about a revolution in the teachers' perspective, as the teaching tools offered through the net were gradually becoming more reliable. Nowadays, the Internet is gaining immense popularity in foreign language teaching and more and more educators and learners are embracing it.

The World Wide Web makes it possible for students to tackle a huge amount of human experience. In such a way, they can learn by doing things themselves. They become the creators not just the receivers of knowledge. Information is presented in a non-linear way and users develop more flexible thinking skills and choose what to explore.

Computers are most popular among students as they are often associated with fun and games. Student motivation is therefore increased, especially whenever a variety of activities are offered according to their level of linguistic competence. Teachers are also responsible for the evaluation of all the web tools offered.

Moreover, it will help students to prepare for further real life situations and to be ready for future work, as learners acquire presentation making study skills which are needed throughout the whole life. In traditional teaching students only were taught by teachers and few tasks were given for self-study. But according to new learner – centered approach and use of HT, teachers have the role of facilitator and they raise learner autonomy and students required to devote a good portion of their time for independent study.

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